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Reference WP: WP1 – Scientific Coordination and Project Management
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General Progress of the action

The overall objective of the consortium is to provide the platform for researchers in Africa, EU, Lebanon and USA to collaborate in training and research activity to implement newborn screening and the comprehensive management of sickle cell disease.

To support the development of individual skills in research, ability to operate new technologies or new systems or policies. Individual staff including senior and early stage researcher's ability to learn statistical analysis and report writing of projects in microbiology, epidemiology and clinical research and contributing to scientific literature in the use of implementation science and community training for sub-Saharan Africa and Lebanon. A number of new or improved skills acquired include the use of isoelectric focusing, haematological practices in diagnosis of SCD, imaging studies for stroke screening and neurological complications in SCD. Researchers have embarked developing research questions for epidemiological studies.

At the institutional level, by implementing new operational policies for staff development such as induction, appraisal and teamwork is essential in the implementation of complex systems by agreeing clear roles and responsibilities within the multidisciplinary team of professionals. Lessons learnt include joint approach between scientists and haematologists in testing and approval of haematological results adapting standard operating procedures (SOPs) from training institutions for emerging centres. New educational materials for the public, schools, patients and their families have either been adapted or through co-production and co-designing created to be culturally appropriate materials.

At the system level, through regular conference calls and emails the importance of communication in service provision has been introduced, especially the need to meet deadlines and practice effective hand over between teams and professionals. The project has introduced version-controlled protocol development so that no protocols lasts longer than three years without it being updated.

Through joint training activities and face to face meetings more cohesive teams are emerging for a sustainable implementation of diagnosis, treatment of SCD and improve the resilience of systems.

The document includes a detailed description of activities and progresses per single work package, the corrective measures to oversee any delays in secondments / activities / deliverables, ethical issues and the updated table of potential risks.